

ATTACHMENT AND VICINITY: EFFECTS ON FEMALES' GREEDINESS

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ABSTRACT

A thorough investigation was done to analyse the catastrophic effect of vicinity and attachment on the greediness of females. The present study took upon samples of 160 females. Participants (80 Urban and 80 Rural) were randomly selected, and their age range was between 16 to 25 years. Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to see the effect of vicinity and attachment on the greediness of females. The result indicates that there is significant effect of vicinity on greediness ($F(1,157) = 8.506, p < .01$) and non-significant effect of attachment on greediness ($F(1,157) = 1.636, p > .05$). Further it was also found that there is a non-significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment on greediness ($F(1,157) = .367, p > .05$). The present findings indicate that urban females had significantly higher greediness as compared to rural females. The implication of the study is to facilitate women that without knowing fact not to mirror others and should not crave materialistic goods if they have to control their greed. Since greed has been proved to be an important source of stress, women can remain stress free if they keep themselves away from unnecessary cravings for materialistic goods shown in the advertisements.

Keywords: Greed; Attachment; Vicinity; Materialistic; Urban and Rural Females

Introduction

Nowadays, health is the prime thrust of an individual. Food, sex, shelter, clothes, and money are all needed to make life livable, and survival is at risk when one or more of these are not accessible at the basic level. It is the birth right of every individual to earn these righteously. There is fine difference between greed and need, and a balance is essential. Greed is the urge to have more and more when it is already adequate and beyond a certain point it is difficult to control. Human greed has always been the subject of reference since the beginning of our civilization (Nikelly, 2006). Greed leads to temptation, which may in the end, turn into an obsession. At this point, one often indulges in unrighteousness to fulfil one's demands and uses unfair means.

The word Greed is translated as "lobha"; it can be described as a feeling of attraction towards materialistic things and the ever-increasing human wants. It disrupts the ability to share and live a fulfilling life. The focus can be towards money, and other tangible material gains. (Kumari, Negi, & Das, 2018) Greediness plays an important role in stress, a person with materialism will always be under pressure because he has hardly any time for relaxation or family. According to Maslow, Human needs are never ending and infinite. When one lower order needs satisfied another higher order need arises if that satisfied another higher need in hierarchy arises. For example, in Maslow hierarchy, if hunger gets satisfied, another need for

higher order safety takes place; if that gets satisfied still a new need of higher order, need for affiliation arises. Fulfilment of all these needs is crucial for the endurance of human beings. Need switch to greed when we feel an intense craving for more and more even when we have already enough. According to Mahatma Gandhi, the father of the nation, “the world has sufficient for everyone’s need but not enough for everyone’s greed”. The issue is one of the balancing priorities Evolutionary viewpoints proposed that greediness as all pervasive and ingrained in human minds. A significant amount of greediness is essential for human wellbeing like productive and reproductive advantages of greed (Greenfeld, 2001; Williams, 2000). The behavioural theory proposed that individuals learn greediness through observation and imitation of surroundings whereas traditionalist advocates that greediness can lead to unethical practices and negative behavior (Tickle, 2004). Aside from material world, greed can manifest itself in the form of selfishness and unwillingness to share with another human being. There are some characteristic features of greed such as, unlimited wants, jealous rage, avarice nature and selfishness.

Need < Desire < Greed

We can explain greed as a three-level stage. It can occur in hierarchy that need at bottom level which means deficiency or lack of something that comes from the requirements as we need food to live and money to buy it. At the middle, desire of things appears. Even after the hunger is satisfied, the need to hog more and a bit more comes in the form of unhealthy desire. The feeling of desire can stem from hearts as well. At the top of the ladder, desire turns into ultimate greed, which is borne from the incessant need to accumulate more material things. Greed can never be satisfied where we crave to have all of it and always want it with us. Even to fulfil our desire, we may destroy someone else's need, giving birth to greed.

Greed is directly or indirectly related to the increasing crime rate in various places. White collar offenders are increased day by day.

The primary motivation for committing a crime included greed, pride, jealousy, anger, economic inequality, etc. Property conflicts and offenders whose main motive is money can lead to serious crime. These white-collar lawbreakers, who rip-off our country of millions and billions in mega fraud, are not poor citizens. There are notable figures in India such as Jeweler Nirav Modi, Vijay Mallya, Mehul Choksi, Lalit Modi and many more offenders who did not account for their obvious crimes and eventually left the country. There can be innumerable reasons for committing serious crimes in this country such as greed, revenge, material gains, ownership, jealousy, selfishness, faulty upbringing behavior are the main reasons. Whereas in the rural areas, the main reason behind crime is family prestige, unemployment, un-education, social discrimination, property disputes, rigid and backward belief, etc. Psychological theories proposed that greed is equal to addiction which is about exploring a reward in the face of risk. Some symptoms of addiction are severe loss of control, craving, dependency, and difficult leaving. A few types of greed function on parallel principles. Addiction and greed both attract control individual mind, an adequate amount was never going to be adequate, and individuals develop tolerance.

Attachment: An Indian concept of attachment means 'MOH' has originated from a verb in Sanskrit language. Society is the building block of our existence as we are social beings. Maslow states that physiological and psychological safety, security, and belongingness need are essential needs for existence and growth. Our innate nature mandates us to be attached to various material things. Attachment can be considered as a natural occurrence in human beings. Nevertheless, attachment can be seen in the form of building emotional relationship that involves an countenance of love and care, giving pleasure and comfort. Attachment can take a negative turn in the form of extreme hoarding balanced attachment is definitely needed for a healthy family (Children, spouse etc.), objects (House, vehicle, property etc.), and professional relationship. While these are positive examples, attachment beyond a certain limit leading to negative causes can be detrimental. They can lead to addiction or obsession. Similarly, attachment to objects that are not attainable causes dissatisfaction or stress.

In personal relationships, attachment towards their own blood related offspring is an intriguing example. A parent feels closer to their child than to someone else's. Personal relationships are important for holding society together but excessive attachment can also appear as unhealthy relationships, or possessiveness which leads to emotional and physical abuse amongst people. Extreme outcomes of attachment can manifest as unlawful behavior, unethical acts, nepotism and corruption, which is a misfortune for the society and the individual himself in the long run.

Human minds can derive pleasure and satisfaction from different forms of attachment. This sense of pleasure multiplies with the subsequent increase in the attachment towards specific things if it is justified by social norms, its moral values and individual guiding values which is useful for social relationship. Moreover, balance level of attachment develops a positive and constructive attitude in the individual, but It can correlate to other different attributes such as human values of service, sacrifices, adventure, heroism, love, compassion, etc. On the other hand, if the society does not justify the attachments as morally desirable or justify it as a socially objectionable. the person is ostracized and eventually becomes an outcast People residing in the urban area increased day by day over the past many decades. Urbanization has a severe impact on people social, economic, personal as well as psychological aspects.

(Kasser&Ahuvia,2001) investigated Materialistic values and well- being in business students. Results include that subject with strongly internalized materialistic values are reported with lower level of self-actualization and happiness and elevated levels of tension, anxiety, mental health issues. (Rosigno& Crowley, 2001), study point out the concept that rural adolescents are protected and sheltered from many social problems like drug and substance abuse, pregnancy, and crime because of their isolation to urban areas, closer ties with family, attachment and spiritual attitude is just the opposite. Otherwise, rural adolescents face all the social problems as their counterpart's face at times, higher rates of episode. (Park & Kim, 2002) conducted a comparative study on community attachment between rural and urban communities in Korea. This study was conducted on 285 urban and rural subjects. The result claimed that Community attachment appeared to be significantly related to group bonds, social participation, community trust, group emotional activities, and cultural and social

environment. The study's main finding as community attachment was significantly higher in a rural community than in the urban community.

(Nikelly's, 2006) study points out that today, greed is responsible for most human distress at both the society and global level. There are many serious consequences to greed like obesity, substance addiction, domestic violence, unsuccessful relationships, child abuse, murder, and other crimes at the community level. The associated probable outcome of greed is massacre, population, excessive poverty, climate change, social instability, and economic crises at the global level. Study also advocates that that human greed, over self-indulgence and selfishness can result in larger global problems. (Shears, Edwards, & Stanley, 2006) study revealed that the American rural area is the safest and secure place to raise a family. Rural adolescents perceived that they live in a sheltered world and do not face many social problems like their urban adolescent counterparts. Results also revealed that using substance among adolescents and youth in rural United States is higher than in urban areas. It is an established knowledge that greed, over self-indulgence, capitalism, addiction narcissism, and acquisitiveness are some of the prominent causes of human suffering throughout recorded history. (North, Wallis, & Weingast, 2009).

(Tunlay, 2011) studied need, greed or opportunity? An examination of who commits benefit fraud and why they do it. The article reviews the profile and motives of benefit fraudsters and used the content analysis method to interpret data. The result shows that different scamming schemes and fraudulent activities are propelled by greed. (Joshi & Raghav, 2012) investigated a comparative study of values among Rural and Urban adolescents. Results revealed that urban adolescents are higher in economic, hedonistic, and power values while rural adolescents are significantly higher in religious and family prestige values. (Barr, 2013) attempted to examine the coping strategies, parental attachment and social support in adolescents concerning their academic stress. The sample size consisted of 700 adolescents selected randomly. The results showed significant relationship in coping strategic, parental attachment and social support with academic stress.

(Najafizadeh et al., 2015) studied a comparative approach between the attachment styles and Mate-selection criteria in Urban and rural girls. The results revealed a marked difference between the girls hailed from rural vs urban areas according to the secure attachment style. (Rawatlal, Pillay & Kliever, 2015) conducted research to analyse socioeconomic status, family-related variables, and caregiver-adolescent attachment. The sample size consisted of 206 families. Results shows that family structure was related with adolescent attachment and household with higher income level were related with low level of anxiousness in relationships. (D'Souza, 2015) studied Greed: Crises, Causes, and Solutions. Their study resulted in understanding of greed that it is the root causes of endless human suffering and larger global issues. The article proposed that greed should be analysed scientifically through the lens of proof based sociological, biological, and psychological interventions because greed is an existential human problem.

(Jaspers & Pieter, 2016) studied the development of materialism across the lifespan. Study conducted on age range 16 to 90 years and a sample of 4,200 subjects. The study revealed

Sample

The present study's sample consisted of 160 subjects (80 Urban and 80 Rural) who were randomly selected. Participant's age group was between 16 years to 25 years.

Tools

1) “Know Yourself” (Greediness & Attachmentscale) by Das & Sharma, 2012

Procedure

The sample was randomly selected from the different graduate and postgraduate colleges in Agra District (Two urban colleges and two rural areas); within the age range of 16-25 years. After explanation of the study purpose Greediness and Attachment scale was administered on the selected sample. The subjects were given the text booklet and requested to complete the name, age, sex, education, and address given on the first page. Instructions of the test were done according to the manual. The filled questionnaire was collected after 30 minutes and the subjects were thanked for their cooperation.

Note: the subjects were categorized on the basis of median of Attachment Scale scores.

Design

- 2×2 Factorial design was used to test the hypotheses.

Statistical Analysis

- Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was calculated

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Analysis of ‘2*2 Factorial Experiments

Is there any effect of vicinity and attachment upon greediness among females.

The hypotheses were framed and prepared to assess the main effects and interaction effect of the two independent variables, 1. Vicinity-Urban/ Rural 2. Attachment- High Attachment/ Low Attachment on dependent variable Greediness.

- ❖ There is no significant effect of vicinity upon the greediness of females.
- ❖ There is no significant effect of attachment upon greediness of females.
- ❖ There is no significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment upon greediness.

Table 4.1: Mean Greediness Scores of Urban and Rural Females Population

VICINITY	N	MEAN	SD
Urban	80	78.37	12.88
Rural	80	72.08	13.72

On the basis of the test scores obtained on the Greediness (80 Urban females and 80 Rural females) the mean score is shown in table 4.1 which shows that the overall mean value of Urban female was 78.37, whereas the average score of Rural females was 72.08. Similarly, SD value of urban was 12.88 and rural was 13.72.

Figure- 4.1: Mean Greediness scores of Urban and Rural Females

It shows that urban females have higher level of Greediness as compared to their rural counterparts.

Table 4.2: Mean Greediness Scores Of High Attachment and Low Attachment Females

ATTACHMENT	N	MEAN	SD
High Attachment	80	76.78	12.65
Low Attachment	80	73.70	14.45

On the second variable Attachment (80 High Attachment and 80 low Attachment) the mean score is shown in table 4.2 which shows that the overall average values of High Attachment females were 76.78. In contrast, the average score of Low Attachment females was 73.70.

The SD value of High Attachment was 12.65 and Low Attachment was 14.45. It shows that High Attachment females have higher level of Greediness as compared to their Low attachment counterparts.

Figure- 4.2: Mean Greediness scores of High and Low attachment Females

It shows that High Attachment females have a higher level of Greediness than their low attachment females counterpart.

Table 4.3: Mean Greediness Score of Urban and Rural Population on the Bases of High Attachment and Low Attachment

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE	ATTACHMENT		MEAN
	High	Low	
Vicinity			Total
Urban	80.26	76.29	78.37
Rural	72.84	71.42	72.08
Total	76.78	73.70	75.23

Table 4.3 shows the mean greediness score of urban high attachment females was 80.26, whereas the greediness average score of Urban low attachment females was 76.29. The finding revealed that the urban high attachment females have a high level of greediness as compared to urban low attachment females' counterparts. Further, the average greediness score of rural high attachment females was 72.84, whereas the average greediness score of rural low attachment females was 71.42. Thus, the score shows that the rural high attachment females have a high level of greediness compared to rural low attachment females counterpart.

Similarly, the mean greediness score of urban high attachment females was 80.26, whereas the greediness average score of rural high attachment females was 72.84. Thus, the score shows that the urban high attachment females have a high level of greediness as compared to

rural high attachment females’ counterparts. Further, the average greediness score of urban low attachment females was 76.29, whereas the average greediness score of rural low attachment females was 71.42. Thus, the score shows that the urban low attachment females have a high level of greediness compared to rural low attachment females counterpart.

Figure- 4.3: Mean Greediness scores of High and Low attachment Females

Further, the mean greediness score of urban high attachment females was 80.26, whereas the average greediness score of rural low attachment females was 71.42. Thus, the score shows that the urban high attachment females have a high level of greediness compared to rural low attachment females’ counterparts. Further, the average greediness score of urban low attachment females was 76.29, whereas the average greediness score of rural high attachment females was 72.84. Thus, the score shows that the urban low attachment females have a high level of greediness compared to rural high attachment females counterparts.

Table 4.4: A 2 X 2 Anova Performed On High And Low Attachment Urban and Rural Females on Greediness Scale

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
Vicinity	1505.510	1	1505.510	8.506**	p<.01
Attachment	289.519	1	289.519	1.636	p>.05
Vicinity * Attachment	64.923	1	64.923	.367	p>.05
Error	27609.427	157	176.984		
Total	934960.000	160			

Effect of vicinity on Greediness: The main effect of the first independent variable Vicinity on dependent variable Greediness was found $F(1,157) = 8.506$, $p < .01$ as statistically highly significant. Average score of urban females was 78.37 whereas the average score of rural females was 72.08. It shows that the urban females have high level of greediness as compared to their rural counterpart. Therefore, hypothesis No. 1 which states that “There is no significant effect of vicinity upon greediness of females” is rejected.

Effect of Attachment on Greediness: The main effect of Attachment on the measure of Greediness was found $F(1,157) = 1.636, p > .05$ as statistically non-significant. Average score of High attachment females was 76.78 whereas the average score of low attachment females was 73.70. It shows that the High Attachment females have a high level of greediness compared to their low attachment females counterpart, but the difference between both groups was non-significant. Therefore, hypothesis No. 2 states that “There is no significant effect of attachment upon females” is accepted. The F-value has been plotted in the below mentioned figure, as follows: -

Interaction Effect of Vicinity and Attachment: The two-way interaction effect between Vicinity and attachment ($V \times A$) on the measure of greediness was found $F(1, 157) = .367, p > .05$ statistically non-significant. This shows there is no interaction between the two variables. Therefore, hypothesis No. 3 which states that “There is no significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment upon greediness” is accepted.

Figure - 4.4 (A): AxB Interaction effect of Vicinity and Attachment on Greediness

The result suggested that the interaction effect of vicinity and attachment has a non-significant as well no interaction effect on the greediness of females. The results are further discussed in next Chapter-5.

Findings, Discussion and Conclusions

The central focus of the present study is to study the effect of attachment and vicinity on greediness of females. Analyses and interpretation of the results of the present investigation lead to the following findings.

1. There is a significant effect of vicinity on Greediness of females.
2. There is no significant effect of Attachment on Greediness of females.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment upon greediness of females.

Discussion

With reference to the present study, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of vicinity on Greediness of females, which shows that urban females are high in greediness

compared to rural females. Thus, there is a direct effect of vicinity on greediness. The reason behind it, may be that in Urban greater rate of industrialization, migration, and population density. Demographic structure and women living in urban areas are exposed to various attractive stimuli. Even white-collar crime rate is also increasing in urban population and the main purpose of crime in urban areas is related to an increasing need for ownership, self-indulgence, jealousy, difficult childhood and behavioral issues. Whereas in rural areas is fond family prestige, unemployment, un-education, social discrimination, property disputes, rigid and backward belief, etc. (Joshi& Raghav, 2012) explained that urban adolescents are higher in economic, hedonistic and power values while rural adolescent's significantly higher in religious and family prestige values. (Sivanesan, 2014) revealed that rural women entrepreneur's reason behind the choice of business because of their family occupation. In contrast, urban women entrepreneurs select the business because it is a self-identity and social status. (Rosigno& Crowley,2001) result suggested that rural adolescents are protected and sheltered from many social problems like drug and substance abuse, pregnancy and crime because of their isolation to urban areas, closer ties with family, attachment and spiritual attitude is just the opposite. (D'Souza, 2015) also suggested that excessive self-indulgence, higher level of greed, and materialism are causes of human suffering and global crises. Federal Bureau of Investigation (2012) reported that the crime rate is high in urban areas and metropolitan cities. (Tunlay, 2011) findings revealed that fraud is motivated by need or greed, with opportunity frequently acting as a stimulus. (Shears, Edwards& Stanley, 2006) result revealed that the American rural area is the safest and secure place to raise a family. Rural adolescents perceived that they live in a sheltered world and do not face many social problems like their urban adolescent counterparts. (Frunzaru&Frunzaru, 2017) explained that a less materialistic way of life is helpful to become generally happier and have life satisfaction.

The finding of the present study indicated that there is no significant effect of attachment on greediness. Its shows that both types of attachment (high and low attachments) have similar effect on greediness. The difference between the mean value of high attachment and low attachment females on greediness can be attributed to chance factors. (Najafizadeh1 et.al., 2015) revealed notable difference between the rural and urban girls with respect to the secure attachment style as rural girls are possess a significantly in a higher secure attachment style compared to their urban counterparts. (Barr, 2013) investigated the Coping mechanism, attachments towards parents and positive help among adolescents with regard to their academic pressure The results indicated that there were marked relationship variables of various coping mechanism, parental attachment and social help groups with academic stress.

The present study also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment on greediness. It can be interpreted that vicinity and attachment do not produced jointly effect on greediness. (Kasser&Ahuvia, 2001)

Has done investigation on values pertaining to materialistic gains and mental wellbeing among business students. The result also pointed that subject who internalized materialistic values intensely are reported lowered levels of self-actualization and happiness, and high level of anxiety, physical symptoms and unhappiness.

Conclusion

Hence, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of vicinity on greediness which shows that urban females are high in greediness. Women living in urban areas are exposed to various attractive stimuli. So, they get attracted by advertisements, objects available in shopping malls etc. This compels them to purchase or acquire more materialistic goods. Hence their greediness is more as compared to their rural counterparts. Simultaneously this study also shows that there is no significant effect of attachment on greediness. Women living in urban areas are also attached to their family members possessions like houses, vehicles etc. Similarly rural women are equally attached to their family members and their belongings such as house, Land, cattles etc. So, there is no significant effect of attachment on greediness. Those with low attachments are also greedy. The present study also reveals that there is no significant interaction effect of vicinity and attachment on greediness. Those with high attachment are greedier irrespective of the vicinity, though the effect is not significant.

Implication of the Study

In the present time technology and modernization drastically change human attitude, behavior and lifestyle as never before. In present times people are acquisitive in their attitude toward society, toward every other individual and self-centered nature. Greediness, jealousy, envy, desire, and selfish behavior is increasing tremendously day by day. Women are suggested not to copy western civilization and should not crave materialistic goods if they have to control their greed. Since greed has been proved to be an important source of stress, women can remain stress free if they keep themselves from unnecessary craving for materialistic goods shown in the advertisements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that the work described has not involved experimentation on humans or animals.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors did not have any conflict of interest.

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